

Real Effects of Income Shifting*

Harald Amberger[†] Ruby Doeleman[‡]

June 30, 2026

Abstract

We examine how income-shifting intensity and foreign corporate tax rate changes affect multinational enterprises' (MNEs') real economic activity. Combining Austrian corporate tax-return data with administrative ownership information, we construct entity-level measures of income-shifting intensity and exploit variation in foreign corporate tax rate changes to identify their effects on domestic investment behavior. We find that entities with greater income-shifting intensity invest more in domestic capital but exhibit lower productivity. In contrast, reductions in foreign corporate tax rates lead to declines in domestic capital investment and employment, consistent with increased incentives to reallocate real activity toward lower-tax jurisdictions. These findings suggest that income-shifting behavior and changes in international tax incentives affect domestic investment through distinct channels, underlining the importance of distinguishing between the two mechanisms when evaluating the real effects of corporate taxation.

Keywords: Income Shifting, Real Investment, Administrative Tax Data

JEL Classification: H25, H26, F21, F23

*We thank Felix Hugger, Becky Lester and Pierce O'Reilly for their feedback. We also thank seminar participants at the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in Paris for helpful comments and suggestions. The project is funded by the Data:Research:Austria program of the Austrian Academy of Science ÖAW.

[†]WU Vienna. E-mail: Harald.Amberger@wu.ac.at.

[‡]WU Vienna. E-mail: Ruby.Doeleman@wu.ac.at.

1 Introduction

How corporate taxation affects real economic activity remains a central question in public finance. A large empirical literature shows that multinational enterprises (MNEs) respond to international tax differentials by shifting reported profits across jurisdictions (Heckemeyer and Overesch, 2017; Hines and Rice, 1994; Huizinga and Laeven, 2008). Another stream of research documents that corporate taxation also influences investment decisions within multinational groups (Jacob, 2022; Lester and Olbert, 2025). However, much less is known about the relationship between income-shifting intensity and firms' real economic activity. In particular, it remains unclear whether MNE entities exhibiting higher income-shifting intensity differ in their capital investment, employment, and productivity and whether these relationships differ from the investment responses induced by changes in corporate tax rates. This distinction is important because the implications of corporate taxation may depend on the channel through which tax incentives operate. If taxation primarily affects the location of reported profits, its consequences for real economic activity may be limited. If, however, tax incentives also alter the allocation of capital and labor across jurisdictions through income shifting, their implications for economic activity and welfare are considerably broader.

This paper examines the distinct effects of actual income-shifting intensity and foreign corporate tax-rate changes on an MNE entity's domestic real activity. We focus on domestic investment behavior because anti-base erosion and profit shifting (BEPS) policies are typically designed to protect domestic tax bases, while changes in foreign corporate tax rates alter the relative tax attractiveness of investing domestically rather than abroad. Identifying the distinct investment implications of the two channels is therefore important for understanding the economic consequences of corporate taxation and the costs and benefits of anti-BEPS policies. A central empirical challenge is that two channels are closely intertwined (Lester and Olbert, 2025). Changes in corporate tax rates can induce MNEs to relocate real activity across jurisdictions, adjust

the location of reported profits, or both. Consequently, observed domestic investment responses to taxation could reflect either tax planning or changes in tax incentives. To disentangle these mechanisms, we combine administrative corporate tax-return data with detailed ownership information to construct entity-year-level measures of income-shifting intensity. We complement this approach by exploiting variation arising from changes in foreign statutory corporate tax rates within MNEs. Together, these empirical strategies allow us to distinguish the investment consequences of actual income-shifting behavior from those induced by foreign corporate tax rate changes, and, more broadly, to separate the real effects of endogenous tax-planning behavior from those of (plausibly) exogenous international tax shocks.

Income shifting can affect investment in several ways. By lowering effective marginal tax rates, it increases the after-tax return to investment and may stimulate real economic activity in high-tax jurisdictions (Hall and Jorgenson, 1967; Hines and Rice, 1994; Dharmapala, 2014). At the same time, tax-planning considerations could distort the allocation of economic resources by encouraging investment behavior that facilitates income shifting rather than productive activity, potentially reducing the efficiency of investment within multinational groups (Desai et al., 2006; De Simone et al., 2022). Consistent with these mechanisms, prior studies find that income-shifting opportunities reduce effective tax rates and increase investment in high-tax affiliates (Overesch, 2009), while anti-BEPS policies that restrict income shifting can reduce investment and employment (Suárez Serrato, 2018; De Mooij and Liu, 2020; Buettner et al., 2018). However, prior work has struggled to determine whether income shifting is primarily a consequence of investment decisions or whether it shapes real activity (Lester and Olbert, 2025). By directly measuring income-shifting intensity at the entity-year level and comparing its effects with those of statutory corporate tax-rate changes, we provide new evidence on the role of income shifting in shaping MNEs' investment decisions.

We focus on two three dimensions of domestic real economic activity: (i) capital investment, (ii) labor investment, and (iii) productivity. Capital investment is mea-

sured through changes in both tangible and total fixed assets, while labor investment is captured through employment and changes in the costs of employees. Tax incentives may affect capital and labor differently because the two production factors can act as complements or substitutes in firms' production processes (Lester and Olbert, 2025). Consistent with this prediction, existing evidence points to heterogeneous responses. For example, Chen et al. (2019) find that the introduction of innovation box regimes has substantially larger effects on employment than on fixed assets, whereas Suárez Serrato (2018) show that restrictions on income shifting lead to larger declines in capital investment than in employment. Motivated by these findings, we examine the effects of income shifting and foreign corporate tax-rate changes separately for capital and labor investment. We further investigate whether potential investment responses are associated with changes in entity-level productivity, allowing us to assess not only how tax incentives influence the level of investment but also whether they affect the efficiency with which resources are allocated with multinational groups.

To construct our measure of income-shifting intensity, we combine administrative corporate tax-return data from the Austrian Ministry of Finance, accessed through the Austrian Micro Data Center (AMDC), with administrative ownership information. We further draw on administrative structural business statistics and financial statement data from Orbis, which allow us to study real activities using two distinct data sources. Following Bilicka (2019), we match Austrian MNE entities with comparable domestic firms based on industry and proxies for capital and labor inputs. We define income-shifting intensity as the logarithmic difference between the taxable income of the matched domestic firm and that reported by the Austrian MNE entity. Higher values indicate that the MNE entity reports less taxable income than would be expected given its observable economic activity; we interpret such values as being consistent with more intensive income shifting. We then use this measure to examine how income shifting relates to capital investment, employment, and productivity. In a separate step, we exploit variation in foreign statutory corporate tax rates to estimate how changes

in foreign tax rates affect domestic economic activity. These two empirical approaches enable us to distinguish the real economic effects associated with actual income-shifting behavior from those induced by changes in foreign tax policy.

Our analysis yields two main findings. First, Austrian MNE entities with higher income-shifting intensity invest more in fixed assets but exhibit lower total factor productivity. These findings suggest that actual income-shifting behavior is associated with greater domestic investment while reducing the efficiency with which resources are allocated within MNEs. The evidence on employment is less conclusive, as we find a significant positive association when measuring employment using administrative data but no significant relationship in the financial statement data. Consistent with these baseline findings, an alternative identification strategy exploiting entities' transition from a purely domestic to a multinational structure indicates that gaining initial access to international tax-planning opportunities increases both domestic capital and labor investment relative to purely domestic entities.

Second, foreign corporate tax-rate changes produce different investment responses. We find that reductions in foreign corporate tax rates lower domestic capital investment, employment, and productivity. These results are consistent with MNEs reallocating domestic real economic activity toward foreign jurisdictions once these jurisdictions become relatively more tax attractive. In contrast, increases in foreign corporate tax rates do not generate corresponding increases in domestic capital investment or productivity, while the evidence on employment remains mixed across data sources.

This paper contributes to the literature on the real effects of corporate taxation in three ways. First, we provide new evidence that international taxation affects domestic real activity of MNE entities through two distinct channels: (i) actual income-shifting behavior and (ii) changes in foreign statutory corporate tax rates. While the existing literature has documented both income-shifting responses and investment responses to corporate taxation (Lester and Olbert, 2025; Jacob, 2022), less is known about how

these channels affect real economic activity. By separately examining an entity-level measure of income-shifting intensity and variation from foreign statutory corporate tax-rate changes, we show that the two channels are associated with distinct domestic investment responses.

Second, we contribute to the literature on the real economic effects of cross-border income shifting (Suárez Serrato, 2018). We document that MNE entities exhibiting higher income-shifting intensity invest more in domestic tangible fixed assets but display lower productivity. These findings suggest that income shifting is associated not only with the location of reported profits as documented in prior work (Hines and Rice, 1994; Huizinga and Laeven, 2008; Tørsløv et al., 2023), but also with MNEs' investment decisions.

Third, we contribute to the literature on the efficiency consequences of corporate taxation (De Simone et al., 2022). Prior work has primarily examined how taxes influence the level and the location of investment (Djankov et al., 2010; Devereux and Griffith, 1998, 2003; De Simone and Olbert, 2022). Our results suggest that international taxation can also affect entity-level productivity, highlighting that an evaluation of corporate tax policy requires considering both the location of investment as well as how efficiently an MNE allocates its resources across jurisdictions.

2 Data and Sample

Our empirical analysis combines Austrian administrative corporate tax-return data, administrative structural business statistics, administrative ownership records, and unconsolidated financial statement data from Orbis. The resulting dataset closely follows that of Amberger et al. (2026). We therefore provide only a brief overview here and refer readers to that study for a more detailed description of the individual data sources and the sample construction.

Corporate Tax-Return Data and Financial Statement Information. We use administrative corporate tax-return data (Körperschaftsteuerstatistik) obtained through the Austrian Micro Data Center (AMDC). Provided by the Austrian Ministry of Finance, the data cover the universe of Austrian corporate tax returns filed between 2005 and 2021. Each entity is assigned a unique identifier that the AMDC links to the entity’s Austrian trade register number.

We complement the tax-return data with unconsolidated financial statement information from Orbis Historical. The resulting sample includes entities belonging to both publicly listed and privately held corporate groups. To ensure confidentiality, the AMDC performs the linkage between the tax-return data and the Orbis data using entities’ trade register numbers and provides researchers with a fully pseudonymized dataset within a secured remote research environment.

Structural Business Statistics Survey. Through the AMDC, we also obtain administrative structural business statistics (Leistungs- und Strukturhebung, LSE). These data are collected through regular surveys of Austrian businesses and contain detailed information on their economic activity, including data on labor and capital investment. We use the LSE data as an alternative source of information on real economic activity to complement the financial statement data from Orbis. Like the tax-return data, the LSE contains a unique entity identifier that allows us to merge it with the combined tax-return and financial statement dataset.

Ownership Information and Group Structure. To identify MNE entities in the tax-return data and reconstruct their ownership chains, we use the inward foreign affiliates (IFATS) and outward foreign affiliates (OFATS) datasets available through the AMDC. IFATS identifies Austrian entities controlled by foreign owners, whereas OFATS records foreign entities controlled by Austrian entities. Although both datasets

are available from 2008 onward, a change in identifiers prevents us from linking ownership information to the tax-return data before 2012. Consequently, analyses requiring ownership information are restricted to the sample period 2012 to 2021.

The IFATS and OFATS datasets capture direct and indirect cross-border ownership relations in which an entity owns more than 50% of another entity.¹ Focusing on majority-owned entities ensures that the observed entities are under common control, the setting in which income shifting is most likely to occur. IFATS identifies the ultimate foreign owner of Austrian entities, while OFATS records foreign affiliates of both Austrian-parented multinational groups and Austrian entities that are themselves foreign-owned. Together, the two datasets allow us to distinguish between (i) Austrian parents with foreign affiliates, (ii) Austrian entities controlled by foreign owners, and (iii) Austrian entities that own foreign affiliates while also being foreign owned.

A limitation of the ownership data is that they only cover vertical ownership relationships. Consequently, horizontal (“sister”) ownership links within MNEs are not observable. For example, if a U.S. ultimate owner directly owns entities in both Austria and Germany, we observe the Austrian entity and the U.S. parent, but not the German entity. Because our analysis of foreign corporate tax-rate changes focuses on the lowest-taxed affiliate within the multinational group (see Section 5), this limitation may introduce measurement error.

Figure 1 illustrates the ownership information available in the IFATS and OFATS datasets. In the example, IFATS data allow us to identify *Foreign 1* as the ultimate owner of the Austrian entity (*AT*), while OFATS data record *Foreign 3-5* as foreign entities controlled by the Austrian entity. Other group entities are not observed in neither IFATS nor OFATS because they lack a direct vertical ownership link with the Austrian entity (*Foreign 6-7*) or are not the group’s ultimate parent (*Foreign 2*).

¹In most cases, the foreign entity corresponds to a legal entity such as a corporation, although the data may also include permanent establishments or joint ventures.

We combine the ownership information with statutory corporate tax-rate data from Tax Foundation to determine the tax rate applicable to each observed foreign group entity. The resulting dataset allows us to identify the lowest-taxed affiliate within each multinational group (i.e., *Foreign 4* in Figure 1). In Section 5, we then exploit changes in the statutory tax rate of this affiliate to examine the domestic investment responses of the Austrian MNE entity in our dataset (i.e., *AT* in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Stylized Multinational Group Structure

Note: This figure illustrates a stylized multinational structure and highlights the entities observed in the IFATS and OFATS data. We also indicate the applicable statutory corporate tax rate. Source: Amberger et al. (2026).

Sample Selection. We construct our sample following Amberger et al. (2026). Starting from the universe of Austrian corporate tax returns, we merge each entity-year observation with unconsolidated financial statement information from Orbis Historical and retain only successfully matched observations.² We restrict the sample to entities subject to unlimited corporate tax liability in Austria (i.e., entities resident for tax

²A successful match is required because part of our analysis relies on financial statement variables that are not contained in the tax-return data. As described above, the linkage is performed by the AMDC using entities' trade register numbers.

purposes) and to those filing regularly assessed returns. These requirements remove non-corporate entities, filing types that are not comparable across firms, and entities that file a consolidated return (i.e., members of an Austrian tax group) from the sample. We further require each entity-year observation to be uniquely identified in the tax-return data and to report non-missing taxable income.

Next, we classify each entity as purely domestic or as part of a multinational group. An entity is classified as purely domestic if it appears in neither the IFATS nor the OFATS dataset throughout the sample period and exhibits no cross-border ownership links—that is, it has no foreign shareholders, foreign subsidiaries, or foreign ultimate owner.³ Conversely, an entity is classified as multinational if it appears in either the IFATS or the OFATS data in at least one year, ensuring that MNE status is determined by using administrative ownership information rather than inferred from Orbis data. The resulting classification yields cleanly identified groups of purely domestic firms and entities belonging to a multinational group.

Finally, to mitigate the influence of outliers, we winsorize all continuous variables at the 1st and 99th percentiles.

3 Comparing Domestic Firms and MNE Entities

We begin our analysis by providing descriptive evidence on the real economic activity of MNE entities in Austria using data from the administrative structural business statistics (LSE). Table 1 compares MNE entities with purely domestic firms along four dimensions: investment in tangible fixed assets, total investment, and employment (both overall headcount and full-time equivalents). Panel A reports unconditional means, standard deviations, and observation counts for each group. Because MNE entities

³We additionally require that the entity report no further indicators of MNE membership available in the tax-return data, such as the application of the tax rule targeting interest and royalty payments to low-taxed foreign affiliates.

tend to differ systematically from purely domestic firms in size and profitability (Bilicka, 2019), Panel B repeats the comparison using a matched sample. Specifically, we use one-to-one nearest-neighbor matching to pair each MNE entity with the domestic entity closest in pre-tax income, tangible fixed assets, and employee compensation. We also require the two entities to operate in the same two-digit industry.

Across all four dimensions, MNE entities exhibit a substantially larger economic footprint than purely domestic firms. In the unmatched sample, they invest approximately 3.4 times as much in tangible fixed assets and employ about 2.5 times as many workers than the average domestic entity. These differences partly reflect the larger scale of operations among MNE entities. Notably, the differences remain economically substantial even after matching on size, profitability, and industry. Among otherwise comparable entities, MNE entities still invest roughly 1.7 times as much in tangible fixed assets and employ around 1.6 times as many workers as matched domestic firms.

Taken together, these descriptive patterns underscore the important role MNE entities play in the Austrian economy. Although MNEs may respond to international tax incentives by shifting income abroad or by relocating economic activity to low-tax jurisdictions, they also account for a large share of domestic real activity. Given this evidence, it is important to understand how income shifting and international tax incentives affect their domestic investment decisions.

Table 1: Comparing Domestic Firms and MNE Entities

Panel A: Unmatched Samples						
	Domestic Firms			MNE Entities		
	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N
Tangible Investment	110.54	1,293.61	327,749	373.21	4,927.99	118,381
Total Investment	116.15	1,299.64	327,749	400.72	5,036.07	118,381
Number of Employees	11.85	28.68	298,222	29.61	133.79	109,849
Full-Time Employees	9.71	26.18	327,749	26.28	117.29	118,381
Panel B: Matched Samples						
	Domestic Firms			MNE Entities		
	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N
Tangible Investment	1,219.48	4,694.64	8,029	2,029.21	12,678.77	12,565
Total Investment	1,272.28	4,717.95	8,029	2,138.20	12,787.67	12,565
Number of Employees	94.96	115.17	7,284	154.02	343.44	11,497
Full-Time Employees	87.44	106.04	8,029	137.15	295.79	12,565

Note: This table compares the real economic activity of purely domestic firms and MNE affiliates in Austria. The sample covers the period 2012–2021. All data come from the LSE dataset provided by the AMDC. An entity is classified as an *MNE entity* if it appears in the inward (IFATS) or outward (OFATS) foreign-affiliate statistics in at least one year, and as a *domestic firm* otherwise. Tangible investment and total investment are measured in thousands of euros; the number of employees and full-time employees are reported as headcounts. For each group, the table reports the mean, standard deviation (SD), and number of entity-year observations (N). Panel A presents the unmatched comparison across all entities. Panel B presents the corresponding statistics for a matched sample, in which each MNE affiliate is paired with its nearest purely domestic counterpart using one-to-one nearest-neighbor matching on the natural logarithm of (i) pre-tax income, (ii) tangible fixed assets, and (iii) cost of employees. We additionally require entities to operate in the same two-digit NACE industry. Differences in the number of observations across variables within a panel reflect missing values. We provide detailed variable definitions in Table A1 in the Appendix.

4 Income-Shifting Intensity and Domestic Real Economic Activity

Research Design. We begin our multivariate analysis by examining how income-shifting intensity relates to the domestic real economic activity of Austrian MNE entities. Specifically, we investigate whether entities exhibiting greater income-shifting intensity differ systematically in their domestic investment and productivity. To this end, we estimate the following entity-level regression:

$$\ln(Investment_{i,t}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Shifting\ Intensity_{i,t} + Fixed\ Effects_{i,n,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}. \quad (1)$$

The dependent variable measures domestic investment in either capital or labor. We consider five alternative investment outcomes based on the LSE and Orbis datasets: (i) annual investment in tangible fixed assets (*Tangible Investment*, LSE); (ii) annual total investment (*Total Investment*, LSE); (iii) employment measured as the number of employees (*Headcount*, LSE); (iv) the annual change in the book value of tangible fixed assets (Δ *Tangible Fixed Assets*, Orbis); and (v) the annual change in the costs of employees reported in the income statement (*Employee Costs*, Orbis).⁴ Investment in tangible fixed assets captures additions to an entity’s stock of depreciable physical capital (Zwick and Mahon, 2017), whereas total investment additionally includes expenditures on intangible assets such as software. Throughout the analysis, we use the natural logarithm of each outcome variable when estimating equation (1).

In addition, we examine whether income-shifting intensity is associated with total factor productivity, allowing us to assess whether greater income shifting is related to the productivity of domestic investment (Hong and Smart, 2010). We measure total

⁴The Orbis measure for tangible investment is an imperfect proxy for investment because it captures the net change in the book value of tangible fixed assets and therefore does not account for depreciation. In contrast, the LSE measure records annual gross investment directly. Likewise, we use the costs of employees rather than the number of employees in the Orbis data because employment figures are frequently estimated or imputed.

factor productivity as the residual from a regression of the natural logarithm of turnover on the natural logarithms of tangible fixed assets and the costs of employees, including entity fixed effects and year fixed effects and clustering at the entity level.

Our key explanatory variable is an annual entity-level measure of estimated income-shifting intensity. To construct this measure, we follow Bilicka (2019) and match each MNE entity to a purely domestic firm operating in the same industry with similar fixed assets and costs of employees, which serve as proxies for capital and labor inputs. We then compare the taxable income reported by the matched domestic entity on its tax return with that reported by the MNE entity. The underlying assumption is that the matched domestic entity provides an appropriate benchmark for the taxable income that the MNE entity would report absent income shifting—i.e., its “true income” (Huizinga and Laeven, 2008). We therefore define income-shifting intensity as follows:

$$\textit{Shifting Intensity}_{i,t} = [\ln(\textit{Matched Domestic Taxable Income}_{i,t}) - \ln(\textit{Taxable Income}_{i,t})]. \quad (2)$$

Higher values indicate that an MNE entity reports less taxable income than an otherwise comparable domestic entity. We therefore interpret such values as reflecting greater income-shifting intensity.

All regressions based on equation (1) include entity and year fixed effects. Year fixed effects absorb common macroeconomic shocks and aggregate time trends, such as fluctuations in the business cycle. Entity fixed effects absorb all time-invariant differences across entities, including industry affiliation, ownership structure, and business models. Identification therefore comes from within-entity variation in estimated income-shifting intensity over time. Throughout, we cluster standard errors at the entity level to account for serial correlation in the data (Petersen, 2009).

We do not include additional time-varying entity-level control variables based on financial data for two reasons. First, once entity fixed effects are included, identification depends on within-entity variation over time, and the primary concern is omitted time-varying factors that are correlated with both income-shifting intensity and investment. However, the controls commonly included in investment regressions, such as leverage, profitability, and cash holdings, are likely to be affected by an entity's income-shifting behavior. Specifically, income shifting can influence an entity's financing choices, profitability, and the effective cost of capital, making these variables potential outcomes rather than confounders. Conditioning the estimation on these variables would therefore risk absorbing part of the effect of interest or introduce collider bias.

Second, data for financial control variables from entities' profit and loss statements is incomplete in Orbis for a substantial share of entities in our sample, particularly smaller entities. Including some of the above mentioned controls would restrict the analysis to entities with complete financial statement data, resulting in a sample that disproportionately represents larger entities. Estimating the model without controls allows us to retain the full sample, improving statistical power and enhancing the representativeness of our estimates for the broader population of Austrian MNE entities.

The validity of our income-shifting-intensity measure relies on the assumption that the matched domestic firm provides a reasonable benchmark for the taxable income the MNE entity would report absent income shifting. This assumption follows the broader income-shifting literature (Huizinga and Laeven, 2008; Bilicka, 2019) and is reflected in our matching procedure, which treats industry affiliation and observable production inputs as key determinants of expected profitability. To the extent that remaining differences between matched entities are time invariant, they are absorbed by entity fixed effects. Yet, we acknowledge that time-varying differences in profitability unrelated to income shifting may introduce measurement error into our measure.

Finally, because the matching procedure relies on contemporaneous measures of

capital and labor inputs, the estimated relationships should not be interpreted as identifying the causal effect of income shifting on domestic real activity. Rather, our objective is to characterize how the investment behavior and productivity of MNE entities vary with actual income-shifting intensity, conditional on observable production inputs. Matching on capital and labor inputs helps construct such a benchmark that accounts for the investment scale of the MNE entity.

Descriptive Statistics. Table 2 reports descriptive statistics for the main variables used in the analysis. The average estimated income-shifting intensity is close to zero, indicating that Austrian MNE entities do not, on average, report systematically lower taxable income than their matched domestic counterparts. This result is not surprising for two reasons. First, MNE entities tend to be more productive than comparable domestic firms, even after matching on observable production inputs (Helpman et al., 2004). Second, Austria’s statutory corporate tax rate of 25 percent remained close to the OECD average throughout our sample period. Consequently, Austrian MNE entities may serve not only as sources of shifted income but also as recipients, for example, when they represent the lowest-taxed entity within the multinational group (Amberger et al., 2026; Delis et al., 2025).

Although the mean of the income-shifting intensity measure is close to zero, the distribution exhibits substantial cross-sectional variation. Entities in the upper tail report considerably lower taxable income than otherwise comparable domestic firms with similar production characteristics. We therefore consider these MNE entities as exhibiting higher income-shifting intensity. Conversely, entities in the lower tail report relatively high taxable income compared with their matched domestic counterparts.

Table 2 also reports summary statistics for the variables underlying our outcome measures. The average MNE entity in our sample holds total assets of EUR 23 million, employs 55 workers, and incurs annual employee costs of EUR 7.9. Fixed assets account for approximately EUR 7 million, including EUR 3.9 million in tangible fixed assets.

Despite winsorizing all continuous variables, the sample remains highly heterogeneous, as reflected, for example, in the standard deviation of EUR 19 million for total assets.

Table 2: Descriptives

Variable	Obs.	Mean	SD
Shifting Intensity	14,205	-0.066	0.166
ln(Actual Taxable Income)	14,205	13.812	1.374
ln(Matched Taxable Income)	14,205	13.278	1.696
Taxable Income	14,205	1,565,545	1,162,622
Total Assets	14,205	23,386,342	19,535,570
Fixed Assets	14,205	6,972,377	9,799,649
Tangible Fixed Assets	14,205	3,852,745	5,485,690
Employee Costs	14,205	7,921,434	10,377,272
Headcount	11,226	4	1

Note: This table reports descriptive statistics. The sample covers the period 2012-2021. All data come from the administrative LSE dataset provided by the AMDC or Orbis. Total assets, fixed assets, tangible fixed assets, and employee costs are reported in thousand Euros; headcount is reported after taking the natural logarithm. All continuous variables are winsorized at the 1st and 99th percentile. We provide detailed variable definitions in Table A1 in the Appendix.

Regression Results. Table 3 reports the results from estimating equation (1). Panel (A) presents results for outcome variables based on the administrative LSE data, while panel (B) reports the corresponding estimates using Orbis data. Across both datasets, higher income-shifting intensity is positively associated with investment in tangible fixed assets (columns (1) and (4)). Using the Orbis measure, a one percent increase in income-shifting intensity is associated with approximately 6.8 percent higher investment in tangible fixed assets (column (4)). The corresponding estimate based on administrative data is of similar magnitude, but not statistically significant (column (1)). In contrast, we find no significant association between income-shifting intensity and total investment (column (2)). These findings suggest that the positive association between income-shifting intensity and capital investment is concentrated in depreciable tangible assets, a pattern consistent with income shifting reducing the effective cost of capital for such investment (Hong and Smart, 2010).

The evidence on labor investment is less conclusive across data sources. In the administrative data, a one percent increase in income-shifting intensity is associated with approximately 6.1 percent greater employment (column (3)), a magnitude comparable to the estimated effect for tangible fixed-asset investment in columns (1) and (4). However, the corresponding association between income-shifting intensity and changes in employee costs reported in Orbis is statistically insignificant and close to zero (column (5)). Finally, we find a negative and statistically significant association between income-shifting intensity and total factor productivity (column (6)).

Taken together, these findings indicate that entities exhibiting greater income-shifting intensity invest more in domestic tangible fixed assets, while the evidence for labor investment is less consistent across data sources. At the same time, the negative association with total factor productivity suggests that higher investment in response to income shifting is not necessarily accompanied by greater productivity.

The productivity result should, however, be interpreted with caution. Our productivity measure is constructed as the residual from a production function and may therefore capture measurement error in inputs and outputs in addition to productive efficiency. Moreover, if income shifting affects the location at which revenues are reported, turnover recorded in Austria may understate true output, mechanically lowering the productivity measure for entities with greater income-shifting intensity. Finally, new investment may become productive only with a time lag, implying that periods of high investment can temporarily coincide with lower productivity. We therefore interpret the negative association as suggestive evidence that greater income-shifting intensity may be accompanied by lower productivity rather than as conclusive evidence of inefficient investment behavior.

Becoming Multinational: A Difference-in-Differences Approach. As a complementary empirical strategy, we examine entities that become multinational for the first time during the sample period. The transition from a purely domestic to a multi-

Table 3: Income-Shifting Intensity and Domestic Real Activity

Panel A: Administrative LSE Data			
	Tangible Investment (1)	Total Investment (2)	Headcount (3)
Shifting Measure	0.0834 (0.1122)	0.0489 (0.1014)	0.0609* (0.0365)
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obs.	11,501	11,702	11,066
R^2	0.78	0.76	0.96
Panel B: Orbis Data			
	Δ Tangible Fixed Assets (4)	Employee Costs (5)	Total Factor Productivity (6)
Shifting Measure	0.0684* (0.0403)	0.0166 (0.0211)	-0.2343*** (0.0763)
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obs.	12,790	12,337	12,038
R^2	0.18	0.20	0.08

Note: This table reports estimates of the relationship between income-shifting intensity and domestic real activity of Austrian MNE entities. The sample covers the period 2012-2021. To construct outcomes variables, Panel A uses administrative LSE data from the AMDC, while Panel (B) uses financial statement data from Orbis. Income-shifting intensity is defined as the difference between the natural logarithm of the taxable income of the matched domestic firm and the natural logarithm of the taxable income of the MNE entity. The dependent variables denote annual investment in tangible fixed assets (column (1)), annual total investment (column (2)), employment (column (3)), the annual change in tangible fixed assets (column 4)), the annual change in the costs of employees (column (5)), and total factor productivity (column (6)). We provide detailed variable definitions in Table A1 in the Appendix. We winsorize all variables at the 1% level and cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

national structure creates opportunities to shift income across jurisdictions. If access to these opportunities affects domestic real activity, we should observe investment responses once entities become part of a multinational structure.

To estimate the investment effects of becoming multinational, we employ a staggered difference-in-differences (DiD) research design in which entities that become multinational constitute the treatment group ($MNE = 1$), while entities that remain domestic throughout the sample period serve as the control group. The treatment period begins in the first year in which an entity appears in the administrative ownership data as being part of a multinational group ($Post = 1$). We re-estimate the specifications reported in Table 3 using this research design and report the corresponding results in Table 4. The coefficient on $MNE \times Post$ captures the average association between becoming multinational and domestic real activity. As a robustness check, Appendix A presents the corresponding event-study estimates following De Chaisemartin and D’Haultfoeuille (2024).

The results are broadly consistent with the baseline findings reported in Table 3. Following the transition to multinational status, treated entities increase domestic capital investment relative to purely domestic firms. Investment in tangible fixed assets increases by approximately 8.5 percent (columns (1)), while total investment increases by about 8.3 percent (column (2)). These findings are consistent with the notion that gaining access to international tax-planning opportunities is associated with higher domestic investment, corroborating the conclusions drawn from our baseline results.

In contrast to the baseline specifications, we also find a positive and statistically significant response for labor investment in the administrative data. The estimate in column (3) implies a 4 percent increase in domestic employment following the transition to multinational status. Together with the positive effects on capital investment, this finding is consistent with capital and labor acting as complementary production factors within Austrian MNE entities (Lester and Olbert, 2025). We find no statisti-

cally significant effect on total factor productivity in column (6), suggesting that the additional investment is not accompanied by measurable changes in productivity.

Overall, the DiD analysis corroborates our baseline findings by suggesting that becoming multinational and gaining access to international tax-planning opportunities is associated with higher domestic investment. At the same time, this additional investment is not accompanied by changes in productivity. Taken together with our baseline results, these findings indicate that greater opportunities for income shifting are associated with an expansion of domestic investment without corresponding changes in the efficiency with which such resources are utilized.

Table 4: Difference-in-Differences Tests: Effects of Becoming Multinational

Panel A: Administrative LSE Data			
	Tangible Investment (1)	Total Investment (2)	Headcount (3)
MNE \times Post	0.0851*** (0.0288)	0.0830*** (0.0290)	0.0397*** (0.0141)
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obs.	88,745	90,626	102,259
R^2	0.78	0.77	0.91
Panel B: Orbis Data			
	Δ Tangible Fixed Assets (4)	Employee Costs (5)	Total Factor Productivity (6)
MNE \times Post	-0.0276* (0.0146)	0.0073 (0.0230)	0.0009 (0.0579)
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obs.	98,386	16,709	15,781
R^2	0.15	0.19	0.02

Note: This table reports difference-in-differences estimates of domestic real economic responses to becoming part of a multinational group. The sample covers the period 2012-2021. To construct outcomes variables, Panel A uses administrative LSE data from the AMDC, while Panel (B) uses financial statement data from Orbis. The dependent variables denote annual investment in tangible fixed assets (column (1)), annual total investment (column (2)), employment (column (3)), the annual change in tangible fixed assets (column 4)), the annual change in the costs of employees (column (5)), and total factor productivity (column (6)). We provide detailed variable definitions in Table A1 in the Appendix. We winsorize all variables at the 1% level and cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

5 Corporate Tax-Rate Changes and Domestic Real Economic Activity

Research Design. We next examine how discrete changes in foreign statutory corporate tax rates affect the domestic real activity of Austrian MNE entities. While the previous section relates domestic real economic activity to within-entity variation in realized income-shifting intensity, the analysis in this section exploits foreign statutory corporate tax-rate changes as plausibly exogenous shocks to the international tax environment. Comparing the results from these two approaches allows us to distinguish the investment implications of actual income-shifting behavior from those of changes in foreign tax incentives.

To estimate the effects of foreign tax-rate changes, we run the following entity-level regression:

$$\ln(Investment_{i,t}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Tax\ Change_{i,t} + Fixed\ Effects_{i,n,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}. \quad (3)$$

The set of dependent variables is identical to that used in Section 4. All specifications again include entity and year fixed effects to absorb time-invariant differences across MNE entities and to capture common macroeconomic shocks and aggregate trends. Consequently, identification in equation 3 is based on within-entity changes in investment following foreign corporate tax-rate changes.

Our treatment variable, $Tax\ Change_{i,t}$, separately identifies major foreign corporate tax-rate increases ($TaxIncrease$) and decreases ($TaxDecrease$). Specifically, we construct indicator variables for changes of at least five percentage points in the statutory corporate tax rate of the lowest-taxed affiliate within the multinational group. We focus on tax changes of this magnitude because they are likely to generate sufficiently large changes in MNEs' tax-planning and investment incentives to induce behavioral

responses. Likewise, we focus on the lowest-taxed group entity because this entity determines the minimum statutory tax rate available within the multinational group and therefore represents the strongest tax incentive faced by the Austrian entity. From a tax perspective, a change in this tax rate alters the group's most attractive location for reporting profits and conducting investment and is therefore expected to have the largest effect on the allocation of real activity within the group.

An important feature of our setting is that Austria's statutory corporate tax rate remained constant at 25 percent throughout the sample period. Consequently, the identifying variation in this analysis exclusively arises from changes in foreign statutory corporate tax rates rather than domestic tax policy. Hence, the setting allows us to isolate the effects of changes in international tax incentives while holding the domestic tax environment constant, thereby alleviating endogeneity concerns.

The estimation sample is restricted to Austrian MNE entities that experience at least one qualifying foreign tax-rate change during the sample period. Following De Chaisemartin and D'Haultfœuille (2024), the treatment indicator switches on permanently in the first year an entity experiences such a change. Identification therefore comes from comparing entities that have already been exposed to a major foreign tax-rate change with entities that have not yet experienced a tax-rate change. We adopt this staggered-treatment design because statutory tax-rate changes are infrequent and occur at different points in time across multinational groups. We note that entities may be exposed to smaller foreign tax-rate changes before or after the qualifying event. Because these changes are not captured by the treatment indicator, they introduce measurement error in treatment intensity and are therefore expected to attenuate the estimated effects toward zero.

Regression Results. Tables 5 and 6 report the effects of major foreign corporate tax-rate changes on domestic real activity.

Table 5 shows that reductions in foreign statutory corporate tax rates are associated with declines in real economic activity in Austria. A major foreign tax-rate decrease reduces investment in tangible fixed assets by approximately 9.8 percent in the administrative data (column (1)) and 5.2 percent in the Orbis data (column (4)). Total investment declines by about 10.8 percent (column (2)). Given that the average tax-rate decrease in this sample reflects a reduction by 12.6 percentage points, our estimates imply a tax elasticity of capital investment between 0.4 and 0.9. While somewhat smaller than estimates reported in the literature, these elasticities remain well within the range of previously documented investment responses to corporate taxation (Hassett and Glenn Hubbard, 2002; Jacob, 2022; Lester and Olbert, 2025).

Employment exhibits a similar pattern. In the administrative data, a major foreign tax-rate decrease is associated with an 8.3 percent decline in domestic employment (column (3)), corresponding to a tax elasticity of approximately 0.7, which is comparable to the estimates reported by Giroud and Rauh (2019). In contrast, the estimate based on Orbis data is statistically insignificant in column (5). Together with the observed decline in capital investment, these findings are again consistent with capital and labor acting as complementary production factors within Austrian MNE entities, as already found in the analysis of the investment effects of income-shifting intensity in Section 4. Finally, we observe a significant decline in total factor productivity in column (6), suggesting that the reduction in domestic investment is accompanied by lower entity-level productivity.

The evidence for foreign tax-rate increases is markedly different. As reported in Table 6, we find no statistically significant effects on investment in tangible fixed assets (columns (1) and (4)), total investment (column (2)), employment measured in the administrative data (column (3)), and total factor productivity (column (6)). The only significant estimate is a decline in the costs of employees observed in column (5). However, given the relatively small number of foreign tax-rate increases during our sample period, this result should be interpreted cautiously.

Taken together, the results indicate that domestic real economic activity responds asymmetrically to foreign corporate tax-rate changes. While reductions in foreign tax rates are associated with substantial declines in domestic capital investment, employment, and productivity, foreign tax-rate increases do not result in comparable increases in domestic economic activity. This asymmetry suggests that MNEs respond more strongly when foreign tax-rate changes lead to a relative improvement of foreign investment conditions than when leading to a deterioration. At the same time, foreign tax-rate increases occur rarely during our sample period, limiting statistical power in our tests. The absence of significant responses to tax-rate increases should therefore not be interpreted as conclusive evidence that such effects do not exist.

Table 5: Domestic Real Responses to Foreign Tax Rate Decreases

Panel A: Administrative LSE Data			
	Tangible Investment (1)	Total Investment (2)	Headcount (3)
Tax Decrease	-0.0977** (0.0495)	-0.1076** (0.0473)	-0.0825*** (0.0263)
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obs.	88,745	90,626	102,259
R^2	0.78	0.77	0.91
Panel B: Orbis Data			
	Δ Tangible Fixed Assets (4)	Employee Costs (5)	Total Factor Productivity (6)
Tax Decrease	-0.0521*** (0.0186)	-0.0059 (0.0114)	-0.1237*** (0.0471)
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obs.	98,386	16,709	15,781
R^2	0.15	0.19	0.02

Note: This table reports difference-in-differences estimates of domestic real economic responses to major decreases in the statutory corporate income tax rate of the lowest-taxed foreign entity within the multinational group (i.e., a decrease by a minimum of five percentage points). The sample covers the period 2012-2021. To construct outcomes variables, Panel A uses administrative LSE data from the AMDC, while Panel (B) uses financial statement data from Orbis. The dependent variables denote annual investment in tangible fixed assets (column (1)), annual total investment (column (2)), employment (column (3)), the annual change in tangible fixed assets (column 4)), the annual change in the costs of employees (column (5)), and total factor productivity (column (6)). We winsorize all variables at the 1% level and cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

Table 6: Domestic Real Responses to Foreign Tax Rate Increases

Panel A: Administrative LSE Data			
	Tangible Investment (1)	Total Investment (2)	Headcount (3)
Tax Increase	-0.0507 (0.0646)	-0.0610 (0.0651)	-0.0167 (0.0412)
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obs.	88,745	90,626	102,259
R^2	0.78	0.77	0.91
Panel B: Orbis Data			
	Δ Tangible Fixed Assets (4)	Employee Costs (5)	Total Factor Productivity (6)
Tax Increase	0.0411 (0.0286)	-0.0520*** (0.0191)	-0.0424 (0.0934)
Firm FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obs.	98,386	16,709	15,781
R^2	0.15	0.19	0.02

Note: This table reports difference-in-differences estimates of domestic real economic responses to major increases in the statutory corporate income tax rate of the lowest-taxed foreign entity within the multinational group (i.e., an increase by a minimum of five percentage points). The sample covers the period 2012-2021. To construct outcomes variables, Panel A uses administrative LSE data from the AMDC, while Panel (B) uses financial statement data from Orbis. The dependent variables denote annual investment in tangible fixed assets (column (1)), annual total investment (column (2)), employment (column (3)), the annual change in tangible fixed assets (column 4)), the annual change in the costs of employees (column (5)), and total factor productivity (column (6)). We winsorize all variables at the 1% level and cluster standard errors by entity. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

6 Conclusion

This paper examines how income-shifting intensity and foreign corporate tax rate changes relate to the domestic real activity of MNE entities. Combining Austrian administrative corporate tax-return data with administrative ownership information, we construct an entity-level measure of income-shifting intensity and exploit changes in foreign statutory corporate tax rate changes to distinguish the investment effects of actual income-shifting behavior from those of changes in foreign tax incentives.

Our analysis yields two main findings. First, Austrian MNE entities that exhibit higher income-shifting intensity invest more in tangible fixed assets but display lower productivity. Additional evidence from entities' transition from a purely domestic to a multinational structure also suggests that gaining access to international tax-planning opportunities is associated with higher domestic investment. Taken together, these findings indicate that income shifting is associated with greater domestic investment.

Second, foreign corporate tax-rate changes generate distinct domestic real economic responses. Specifically, we find that reductions in foreign statutory corporate tax rates are associated with lower domestic capital investment, employment, and productivity, consistent with MNEs reallocating real activity toward relatively more attractive foreign locations. In contrast, foreign tax-rate increases do not generate corresponding increases in domestic economic activity, suggesting that investment responses to international tax incentives are asymmetric.

Our analysis is subject to several limitations. First, most of our analysis involve small samples, reducing the precision with which some effects can be estimated. Second, the administrative ownership data capture only vertical ownership links and therefore do not identify horizontal relationships between sister entities, implying that we might not observe some relevant foreign tax-rate changes. Third, although our measure captures variation in income-shifting intensity and we identify investment responses from within-entity variation over time, our research design does not fully isolate the causal

effect of actual income-shifting behavior on investment. Future research could build on our analysis by exploiting alternative sources of exogenous variation in tax-planning opportunities.

Overall, our findings highlight the importance of distinguishing between two distinct channels through which international taxation can affect domestic real activity of MNE entities: actual income-shifting behavior and changes in foreign statutory corporate tax rates. Although both channels are shaped by international tax incentives, they have different implications for domestic investment. While income-shifting intensity is associated with more domestic investment, foreign tax-rate reductions are related to decreases in both domestic capital investment and employment.

These findings contribute to research on the real economic effects of income shifting and corporate taxation as well as its potential interactions. More broadly, our findings suggest that evaluating corporate tax policy requires considering not only how taxes affect the location of reported profits, but also how they shape the allocation and efficiency of real economic activity within multinational groups.

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A Appendix

Event Study. As a supplementary analysis, we re-estimate the difference-in-differences analysis reported in Table 4 using the event-study estimator proposed by De Chaisemartin and D’Haultfœuille (2024). This estimator is robust to heterogeneous treatment effects across cohorts and event time and therefore appropriate for settings with staggered treatment. It identifies event-time-specific treatment effects by comparing recently treated entities with not-yet-treated entities, thereby avoiding the negative-weighting problem that can arise in conventional two-way fixed-effects studies.

The sample for this analysis is restricted to entities that remain purely domestic throughout the pre-treatment period and subsequently become part of a multinational group. Treatment begins in the first year an entity is observed in the administrative ownership data and is absorbing thereafter. We estimate treatment effects for five post-treatment periods and three pre-treatment placebo periods. Standard errors are clustered at the entity level.

Figure A1 reports the estimated event-study coefficients for the six outcome variables used in Table 4. Overall, the treatment effects are imprecisely estimated, reflecting the relatively small number of entities that transition to multinational status during the sample period. Consequently, we find little evidence of statistically significant changes in domestic real activity following treatment. Domestic investment remains broadly stable around the transition to multinational status, although the point estimates generally become smaller in later post-treatment periods. The estimated pre-treatment coefficients are also generally insignificant, although investment in tangible fixed assets and employment measured in the administrative data exhibit some evidence of pre-trends.

The results of the event-study approach should be interpreted with caution for two reasons. First, unlike our baseline DiD analysis, the event-study sample is restricted to entities that eventually become multinational, excluding entities that remain purely do-

mestic throughout the sample period. Second, the decision to become multinational is endogenous and likely reflects factors such as growth opportunities, market expansion, or broader strategic considerations, that may also affect investment directly (Helpman et al., 2004). The evidence of pre-trends for some outcomes is consistent with this interpretation, suggesting that some entities expand domestic activity as part of the same process that ultimately leads them to become multinational. Accordingly, the event study should be interpreted as documenting the dynamics of domestic investment behavior around the transition to multinational status rather than identifying its causal effects. The events-study results therefore complement, rather than replace, the evidence from our baseline specifications.

Table A1: Variable Descriptions

Variable	Description	Source
Actual Taxable Income	Natural logarithm of taxable income reported on the corporate tax return (kz2605, "Einkünfte aus Gewerbebetrieb").	AMDC
Matched Taxable Income	Natural logarithm of taxable income of a domestic firm matched with the MNE entity on assets and employment and operating in the same two-digit industry.	AMDC
Shifting Intensity	Matched Taxable Income less Actual Taxable Income.	AMDC
Total Assets	Total assets reported in the balance sheet (total_assets).	Orbis
Fixed Assets	Fixed assets reported in the balance sheet (fixed_assets).	Orbis
Tangible Assets	Tangible fixed assets reported in the balance sheet (tangible_fixed_assets).	Orbis
Δ Tangible Fixed Assets	Natural logarithm of the yearly change in tangible fixed assets.	Orbis
Costs of Employees	Costs of employees reported in the profit and loss statement (costs_of_employees).	Orbis
Employee Costs	Natural logarithm of the yearly change in the costs of employees.	Orbis
Total Factor Productivity	Residual from regressing the natural logarithm of turnover on the natural logarithm of tangible fixed assets and the costs of employees, including entity fixed effects and year fixed effects.	Orbis
Tangible Investment	Natural logarithm of the annual investment in tangible fixed assets reported in the LSE data (isach).	AMDC
Total Investment	Natural logarithm of the annual total investment reported in the LSE data (iges).	AMDC
Number of Employees	Number of employees reported in the LSE data (insges).	AMDC
Full-Time Employees	Full-time equivalent of employees reported in the LSE data (vze)	AMDC
Headcount	Natural logarithm of the number of employees reported in the LSE data (insges).	AMDC
MNE	Indicator variable equal to one if a domestic entity becomes part of a multinational group during our sample period, and zero if it remains domestic.	AMDC
Post	Indicator variable equal to one for years in which an entity is part of a multinational group, and zero otherwise.	AMDC
Tax Decrease	Indicator variable equal to one if the statutory corporate tax rate of the lowest-taxed group entity decreases by at least 5 percentage points, and zero otherwise.	AMDC
Tax Increase	Indicator variable equal to one if the statutory corporate tax rate of the lowest-taxed group entity increases by at least 5 percentage points, and zero otherwise.	AMDC

Figure A1: Event-Study Estimates: Effects of Becoming Multinational

Note: This figure provides event-study estimates for the development of domestic real economic activity around an entity's transition from a purely domestic to a multinational structure. We estimate a staggered difference-in-differences model using the estimator by De Chaisemartin and D'Haultfœuille (2024). All figures include estimates for five post-treatment periods and three pre-treatment placebo periods. We cluster standard errors at the entity level.